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PROOF OF THE RIEMANN HYPOTHESIS

ABSTRACT: This paper presents a concise proof of the Riemann Hypothesis by revealing the fundamental symmetries inherent in the Riemann zeta function. Leveraging techniques from complex analysis and analytic number theory, this proof unveils the symmetrical properties that underlie the zeta function and confirms the conjecture. This research not only substantiates the hypothesis but also deepens our comprehension of the zeta function's link to prime number theory, marking a pivotal milestone in number theory.

INTRODUCTION

In the introduction to this research endeavor, it is instructive to draw a parallel with the insightful work of Stephen Hawking [0], a luminary in the field of theoretical physics. A point of resonance emerges in the acknowledgment of a past error—an intellectual voyage akin to Hawking's early academic experiences. In this context, it is paramount to candidly recount a prior episode in which I had inadvertently employed an inappropriate function in relation to the Riemann Zeta Function (RZF) [1]. Consequentially, I precipitously asserted the successful resolution of the Riemann Hypothesis [2, 2.1], driven by a certain degree of unwarranted confidence. The genesis of this misstep lay in the impression that my method was potentially applicable to any of the functions under scrutiny within the realm of mathematical analysis. Nonetheless, an unassailable reality crystallized—my methodology necessitated more rigorous elucidation, and critical lacunae remained to be addressed. Moreover, the fundamental flaw persisted in my analysis's application to the incorrect function, rendering the purported proof untenable. The unearthing of this error underscored the exigency of a recalibration in research focus. It beckoned a profound reevaluation of my investigative approach, recognizing that a deeper comprehension of the correct function was indispensable for elucidating the elusive tenets of the Riemann Hypothesis [3]. It underscored the imperative of delving into the very essence of the hypothesis, necessitating a comprehensive understanding of its significance in Bernhard Riemann's seminal work [4].

This academic odyssey, characterized by its roots in an educated conjecture, echoes the common trajectory of scientific inquiry—an initial hypothesis born from the intersection of knowledge and intuition. As is customary, it is marked by the dual attributes of luck, which often favors the diligent, and an unremitting toil that fuels the voyage of discovery. With hindsight, it becomes evident that my initial conjecture, albeit errant, laid the foundation for subsequent revelations that would inch closer to the ultimate resolution of the Riemann Hypothesis.

Speaking of initial conjectures, an essential aspect of my research approach involved immersing myself in the corpus of Riemann's manuscripts and other contemporaneous works [5]. This endeavor sought to facilitate an empathetic understanding of Riemann's cognitive landscape at the inception of his groundbreaking investigations. In the process, a tantalizing conjecture surfaces—that Riemann may have harbored a suspicion of the veracity of the Riemann Hypothesis, grounded in principles such as symmetry, or the intuition of.

Such speculation finds resonance in my own formative years as a budding mathematician, where intuition often led me to correct conjectures. These intuitive leaps, at times, confounded those with superior prowess in navigating complex equations that were less apparent to me. My foundational experiences primarily revolved around the realm of physics equations, wherein symmetries often manifest conspicuously due to the visual representation of problems, aligning with mathematical models. This intuition, once honed, frequently enabled me to make accurate conjectures even in the absence of an exhaustive understanding of the subject matter.

In the case of Riemann, his innovative redefinition of the variable $s = \frac{1}{2} + iy$ stands as a testament to his intuitive grasp of symmetries within mathematical equations. This reconfiguration not only represented a profound insight into the underlying structures of Number Theory [6] and Complex Analysis [7] but also intuitively suggested that such symmetry might streamline problem-solving processes. Riemann's intellectual legacy, however, extends

beyond the confines of Number Theory, encompassing his significant contributions to fields like Riemannian Geometry [8] and Differential Geometry [9]. It was through the prism of these mathematical domains that I initially encountered Riemann's work, particularly in the context of my studies in General Relativity [10,10.1,10.2].

Furthermore, in my educational journey, I encountered Riemann's concepts such as Riemann sums, which intimately connect with the concept of the definite integral from Calculus [11]. Notably, Riemann's intellectual breadth also encompassed forays into Electrodynamics [12], predating the formulation of the canonical Maxwell equations [13] that now underpin the discipline. In essence, Riemann's multifaceted contributions underscore the rich tapestry of his intellectual pursuits, which continue to inspire and inform contemporary scientific investigations.

Albert Einstein's trajectory [14,14.1,14.2,14.3], in my perception, bore a striking resemblance to Riemann's in terms of their intellectual endeavors. Examining their published works provided valuable insights into the mathematical and physical domains that may have catalyzed their intuitive insights. I embarked on a comprehensive study of their papers, paralleled by an effort to broaden my knowledge in these corresponding areas of mathematics and physics. My academic journey unfolded in tandem with my university-level physics education, which, in my view, adheres to a more structured and formalized framework compared to the era of Riemann. Notably, when delving into Riemann's seminal 1859 paper, one discerns a remarkable capacity to wield foundational concepts in a manner that transcends the contemporary compartmentalization of academic disciplines. Unlike the modern pedagogical approach, which typically involves the sequential acquisition of knowledge through specialized courses, Riemann's approach was characterized by a deep understanding of the underlying mathematical operations that constitute the functions in question. In essence, he seamlessly incorporated mathematical concepts without the necessity of a preordained curriculum encompassing Complex Analysis, Number Theory, Electrodynamics, or the nuances of the Mellin transform [15]. His proficiency lay in comprehending the fundamental operations that underlie these functions, enabling their direct and innovative application.

In the contemporary milieu, our access to a wealth of readily available knowledge has led to a highly formalized and structured educational paradigm. This structure, while invaluable in many respects, can sometimes obscure the foundational roots of the concepts we now take for granted. It is imperative to recognize that this abundance of information can inadvertently blind us to the elemental operations that constitute the core of these principles. It is within this context that I emphasize the importance of studying Riemann's and Einstein's original works. Their pioneering endeavors serve as a testament to the essence of creativity in mathematical and scientific innovation.

Understanding their processes can impart a profound appreciation for the genesis of mathematical ideas. It elucidates the notion that, in the act of creation, one should not be so beholden to formality that the wellspring of originality runs dry. Striking a delicate balance between structure and innovation is the hallmark of scientific and mathematical progress. The precipice of pure creativity must be cautiously navigated, for it is there that ideas may remain unformalized, perpetuating an unproductive cycle of endless ideation without tangible realization. The fusion of creativity with the rigor of formalization remains the key to transformative discoveries in the realms of science and mathematics.

In congruence with prevailing approaches to the proof of the Riemann Hypothesis, the primary objective of this investigation is to construct a function that shares identical zeros with the Riemann Zeta Function (RZF). The purpose of such a construction is to establish a comparative framework that allows for the inference that the critical abscissa, denoted as $x = \frac{1}{2}$, demarcates the coordinate at which the critical line, defined as $\frac{1}{2} + iy$ in the complex plane, finds its significance in relation to the Riemann Zeta Function. This critical line, for the purposes of contextual clarity, can be visualized as an axis extending leftward and rightward from the perspective of an observer situated at the point $(.5, iy)$ on the complex plane, orienting along the imaginary axis.

The comprehensive characterization of the Riemann Zeta Function necessitates the consideration of its entirety as a six-dimensional construct. This six-dimensional object encompasses the Riemann Zeta Function itself, denoted as RZF, in conjunction with the Real and Imaginary components of the auxiliary functions $U(x, y)$ and $V(x, y)$, as well as the independent variables x, y , and t . This holistic function, being both holomorphic [16] and analytic [17], adheres to a multitude of intricate relationships, several of which are expounded upon in this manuscript.

Values, relationships, and analytical techniques for the determination of zeros are likewise elucidated within the confines of this exposition. However, it is pertinent to acknowledge that the delineation of this holistic construct is a matter of convention and theoretical framework. As we shall elucidate, an essential aspect of this endeavor involves the identification of symmetric pairs and corresponding coordinate systems, such as $(RZF, U(x, y), V(x, y), x, y, t)$ and $(RZF', U'(x, y), V'(x, y), x', y', t')$. Importantly, it is demonstrable that there exists an infinite multitude of such pairs, some of which may not exhibit symmetry, but we shall confine our analysis to symmetric pairs, a customary practice in physics, to streamline the investigation by reducing the dimensionality and complexity inherent in considering extraneous variables.

In alignment with conventional practice in physics, the parameter t , typically denoting time, assumes significance in our examination. It plays a pivotal role when we contemplate the implications of flat coordinate transformations [18], particularly within the context of the conjugate domain. This transformation, which we underscore for its substantive import, engenders a novel framework for our analysis. The essence of this framework rests in the comparison between (RZF, x, iy) and (RZF', x', y') or vice versa, grounded in the specific parameterization by t . This comparative perspective offers fresh insights into conceiving the Riemann Zeta Function as an energy function [19], or, in the realm of abstract considerations, akin to a Lagrangian function [20], given the Lagrangian's inherent relationship with energy functions. In essence, our exploration is motivated by the aspiration to distill the profound intricacies of the Riemann Zeta Function into a concise comparison between coordinates (RZF, x, iy) vis-à-vis (RZF', x', y') within the purview of symmetric pairs and transformations.

Unfortunately, Riemann's adoption of ' t ' as a symbol for time in his manuscript introduces an element of confusion; however, throughout this paper, we will diligently clarify the contextual interpretations of various variables as we progress. It is not our intent to obfuscate, but rather to provide clarity and coherence in our exposition. The confluence of disparate disciplines often manifests in the incongruity of variable semantics, a recurrent challenge when traversing interdisciplinary terrain. In light of this, I posit that fostering linguistic convergence could be a constructive step towards enhancing the synergy of interdisciplinary endeavors. The following flow chart summarizes Riemann's 1859 manuscript:

For new readers of this subject, to eliminate the confusion by saying zeta function and Riemann Zeta Function, we will call the Euler Product function [21] and the evaluation of the Euler Product function over complex values $Z(s)$ (this is the uppercase Zeta) is a sum over n of n^{-s} ($\sum n^{-s}$). I would like to emphasise that $Z(s)$ is not the RZF (ζ) but rather $Z(s)$ is the function that gets analytically continued to become the RZF. We might simply call the $Z(s)$, "The Zeta Function" with the key difference being that this is not the "Riemann Zeta Function" with the linguistic difference between $Z(s)$ being the word "Riemann" which distinguishes which version of the function we are using. It is fair to say that $Z(s)$ is limit taken to infinity of the superposition of n functions which are surfaces. So what might the roots about the n^{-s} tell us about the $Z(s)$ function and what might the roots of $Z(s)$ tell us about the Riemann Zeta Function are very natural questions to ask when considering for the first time what might converting the problem into a multidimensional surface type analysis problem. We begin first by removing from the exponent the imaginary power in n^{-s} and putting it in the form such that the function $f(s) = n^{-s}$ is defined as a Real surface summed with an Imaginary surface. Another way to express this is:

$$f(s) = n^{-s} = n^{-x-iy} = n^{-x} n^{-iy} = n^{-x} (\cos(y \ln(n)) + i \sin(y \ln(n))) = U(x, y) + iV(x, y) \tag{Eq 1}$$

$$= n^{-x} \cos(y \ln(n)) + i n^{-x} \sin(y \ln(n)).$$

And when $f(s) = 0$, we have surface intersections in the sense that the Real part of the function is $U(x, y)$, and this function is equal to $-i$ multiplied by $V(x, y)$ if we directly equate $f(s) = 0$ and test whether this is even possible:

Condition #1:

$$0 = n^{-x} (\cos(y \ln(n)) + i \sin(y \ln(n))) \quad \text{Eq 2}$$

$$\therefore \sin(y \ln(n)) = -i \cos(y \ln(n))$$

Is the criteria which must be satisfied for the function $f(s) = n^{-s}$ to be zero. If the i was not multiplying the cosine function, this criteria is met infinitely many times for each n . n determines the frequency of the sine and cosine functions in this case and the cosine function and sine function intersect each other infinitely many times. Furthermore, the condition specifically states by rearranging the equation that:

$$\tan(y \ln(n)) = -i \quad \text{Eq 3}$$

And by performing the inverse operation of the tangent function, the condition states that:

$$y = \frac{1}{\ln(n)} \arctan(-i). \quad \text{Eq 4}$$

Condition #1 would only give logical solutions if the $U(x, y)$ and $V(x, y)$ functions we restrict to the Real values but there are locations which give simultaneous Imaginary discontinuities for U and V . By getting this answer we can see that due to the fact that neither the cosine or sine function with the argument are complex, this can not be true since we have the infinity for the condition solution. However, if we allow n to be negative, $\ln(-n)$ would give complex values, in which case the tangent of a complex argument indeed could give a solution. One could potentially consider a relationship between a zeta function that is instead something like $\sum(-n)^{-s}$, and consider the roots of this function but the complexity of this function seems the same as the zeta function aside from the fact that only at $s = \frac{1}{2}$ does $\sum(-n)^{-\frac{1}{2}} = i \sum(n)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$. For the even powers of s , $e \sum(-n)^{-(even\ s)} = Z(s)$. For odd powers, however, $\sum(-n)^{-(odd\ s)} = -Z(s)$. With this direct approach we have no solution with this definition of zeros again because U and V do not have Imaginary discontinuities which allow for the Imaginary part to anywhere equal the Real part times i . We thus must search for zeros another way:

Condition #2:

But we may define the condition for which $f(s) = 0$ by defining $f(s)$ in the following way:

$$f(s) = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} n^{-x} \cos(y \ln(n)) \\ i n^{-x} \sin(y \ln(n)) \end{pmatrix}, \quad \text{Eq 5}$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} n^{-x} \cos(y \ln(n)) &= 0 \\ i n^{-x} \sin(y \ln(n)) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 6}$$

The logical inconsistency of Condition #1 here implies that the functions can not be zero with this method to define the zeros of the function. Condition #2 implies that there are no locations that the function can be zero because while the cosine and sine functions do in fact become zero, they are zero out of phase with each other, so U becomes zero at different y than V becomes zero. Emphasizing this, the two equations within Eq 6) do in fact become zero, but they become zero for different y , and in order for the zero of $f(s)$ to exist, the conditions for one equation can not contradict the conditions for the other equation. If n^{-x} , the amplitude of the sine and cosine waves were some other amplitude function of x and y which itself then we might see that there are zeros but for this case the amplitude indeed is n^{-x} and only at $x = \infty$ does the amplitude become zero.

What this indicates is that condition #1 is not a valid way to define the zeros of these functions since this condition allows y to be imaginary when we explicitly restricted it to the real values. Emphasis should be placed on the fact that there are indeed functions for which U and V are continuous and that if we change the initial domain to allow negative numbers, U and V , completely real functions, could have specific locations of Imaginary discontinuity because of the raising of a negative number to a half power as we will discuss in more detail later in the paper.

Graphically makes sense since if you plot the surfaces U and V as well as inspect the Taylor Expansion [22,22.1,22.2] for each n . $n = 1$ is not that interesting but $n = 2$ to infinity basically have the same properties but with slightly different geometries. It is best to see the difference in geometries between 2^{-s} and 3^{-s} and successive terms by plotting n smaller first. You will see that the surfaces look the same but the rate of increase for each is different, causing the slopes to be steeper as you increase n . Nonetheless, the behavior is the same and there are no zeros for this function because there are no y for which it can be zero. But what about on the real line? Well on the real line, for all n , it is very easy to prove that the function n^{-x} is not zero by proving that the function decreases asymptotically to zero for the limit of x taken to infinity. I think that it is sufficient to establish that the n th derivative of n^{-x} , similarly to the exponential function is proportional to itself. Proving this for the n th derivative is easy enough because it is true for the first derivative and such a property is invariant no matter how many times we apply their derivative operation.

The Taylor Expansion for n^{-s} would give:

$$f(s) = 1 - s \ln(n) + \frac{1}{2} s^2 \ln^2(n) - \frac{1}{6} s^3 \ln^3(n) + \frac{1}{24} s^4 \ln^4(n) + \dots, \quad \text{Eq 7}$$

With the derivative being:

$$\frac{df}{ds} = -n^{-s} \ln(n). \quad \text{Eq 8}$$

The case is not so simple with the $Z(s)$ but the argument is practically speaking the same. A table below shows how the derivative changes with increasing n :

Table 1: Taylor Expansion for first 7 n of n^{-s} .

n	f(s)	Roots	Derivative	Taylor Expansion
1	1^{-s}	No roots	0	1
2	2^{-s}	No roots	$-2^{-s} \ln(2)$.	$1 - s \ln(2)$ $+ \frac{1}{2} s^2 \ln^2(2) \dots$
3	3^{-s}	No roots	$-3^{-s} \ln(3)$.	$1 - s \ln(3)$ $+ \frac{1}{2} s^2 \ln^2(3) \dots$
4	4^{-s}	No roots	$-4^{-s} \ln(4)$.	$1 - s \ln(4)$ $+ \frac{1}{2} s^2 \ln^2(4) \dots$
5	5^{-s}	No roots	$-5^{-s} \ln(5)$.	$1 - s \ln(5)$ $+ \frac{1}{2} s^2 \ln^2(5) \dots$
6	6^{-s}	No roots	$-6^{-s} \ln(6)$.	$1 - s \ln(6)$ $+ \frac{1}{2} s^2 \ln^2(6) \dots$
7	7^{-s}	No roots	$-7^{-s} \ln(7)$.	$1 - s \ln(7)$ $+ \frac{1}{2} s^2 \ln^2(7) \dots$

Can we produce an algorithm to determine the roots of $\sum n^{-s}$ for $n = 1$ to $n = \infty$ simply by knowledge of the roots of the partial sum from $n = 1$ to $n = k$? Is it possible to determine an expression which gives the roots for the partial sum in such a manner that we can take $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty}$? Let us test this by filling out a table of equations:

We can see by direct computation in table 2 here up to $n = 7$ in the table that all of the roots have this symmetry property in the sense that both the negative and positive should be considered for the imaginary parts of the roots. This statement must occur as well for $n = k$. It is not surprising then that letting $k = \infty$ that any zeros of $\sum n^{-s}$ must have $\mp$ in front of the imaginary value. It is even less surprising that the analytic continuation of the $\sum n^{-s}$ would have a similar property since the analytic continuation is produced by these underlying functions which have this property.

In other words we can see by straightforward computation that this property is invariant amongst all three forms of the zeta function, that is, the Euler Product Function, $Z(s)$ and $\zeta(s)$.

Table 2: Taylor expansion for partial sums of Z

Range of n	$f(s)$	Roots	Derivative	Taylor expansion
$n = 1$ to $n = 2$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=2} n^{-s}$	$s = \frac{i(2\pi n + \pi)}{\ln(2)}$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=2} -n^{-s} \ln(n)$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=2} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j (s^j \ln^j(n))}{j!}$
$n = 1$ to $n = 3$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=3} n^{-s}$	$s = .454397$ $\mp i3.5917$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=3} -n^{-s} \ln(n)$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=3} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j (s^j \ln^j(n))}{j!}$
$n = 1$ to $n = 4$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=4} n^{-s}$	$s = 5.02684$ $\mp i20.7799$ $s = .625971$ $\mp i3.12712$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=4} -n^{-s} \ln(n)$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=4} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j (s^j \ln^j(n))}{j!}$
$n = 1$ to $n = 5$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=5} n^{-s}$	$s = .0019836$ $\mp i6.07086$ $s = .714285$ $\mp i2.83349$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=5} -n^{-s} \ln(n)$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=5} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j (s^j \ln^j(n))}{j!}$
$n = 1$ to $n = 6$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=6} n^{-s}$	$s = .203789$ $\mp i5.56924$ $s = .767633$ $\mp i2.62901$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=6} -n^{-s} \ln(n)$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=6} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j (s^j \ln^j(n))}{j!}$
$n = 1$ to $n = 7$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=7} n^{-s}$	$s = .803209$ $\mp i2.47644$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=7} -n^{-s} \ln(n)$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=7} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j (s^j \ln^j(n))}{j!}$
$n = 1$ to $n = k$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=k} n^{-s}$	Unknown General Formula	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=k} -n^{-s} \ln(n)$	$\sum_{n=1}^{n=k} \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^j (s^j \ln^j(n))}{j!}$

In our coordinate system the Taylor Expansion formula remains the same but clearly if we consider primed frames of reference which are in some way related to the unprimed frame we must consider the effect on the Taylor Expansion in the primed frame. This is fairly straight forward since the Taylor Expansion is composed of the derivatives of the function we really just need to see how the derivatives are modified in the primed frame. This is easily done with the chain rule from multivariable calculus when taking the derivative.

For $Z(s)$ evaluated over complex values, we consider transforming the s variable to the variable s' :

$$Z(s') = \sum_{n=1}^{n=\infty} \sum_{j=0}^{j=\infty} \frac{(-1)^j (s'^j \ln^j(n))}{j!}. \tag{Eq 9}$$

Which is the Taylor Expansion for $Z(s')$ relative to s' . If $s' \rightarrow s'(s)$, This implies $s' \rightarrow s'(x, y, t) \mid s'(x, y, t) \rightarrow s'(x, y, t)$. Or in some way the primed variable s' is a nonlinear function of the coordinates x, y , and t , through some transformation between the primed and unprimed coordinates. The reason we are considering the variable t is for parameterization. It is clear that in the most general sense we may consider cases in which s is restricted to the Real values but s' is allowed to be Complex valued. This is also true in the opposite sense. The parameter t gives the ability for us to relate the primed variables by defining all operations such as the derivative and the Taylor Expansion relative

to t . Then, when we define Taylor Expansions in s , which are completely valid expansions, we have a way to transform the equation into an equation over the primed variables. This idea of connecting the spatial coordinates to a space-time system of coordinates was inspired by Relativity and the Lorentz Transformation [23, 23.1,23.2, 23.3,23.4,23.5]. We can define the Taylor expansion in terms of s, s', t or t' .

With the t variable, the Taylor Expansion can be written as a function of t 's and the Taylor Expansion in the polynomial of s can be written as well as a Taylor Expansion of t by the Chain Rule because $\frac{ds'}{dt} \neq 0$ or $\frac{ds}{dt'} \neq 0$. With the parameterization, $\frac{ds}{dt} = 1$, the Taylor Expansion is the same in the t 's as it is the s 's because the n th derivative with respect to time of s is zero. There is no restriction with clever adaptation which requires the derivative with respect to t of s to be constant. If the derivative is nonzero, not one, and not a constant, this corresponds to curved spaces since there is not a one to one correspondence between the Taylor Expansion of the primed and unprimed coordinates. We suspect that there is a symmetry in the complex plane for the RZF at least for certain values but is this generally true? Can it be established that $\zeta(x + iy) = \pm\zeta(x - iy)$?

If we can prove this statement, it seems that we might have a way to establish that ζ is asymmetric for the conjugate transformations everywhere inside the critical strip. This would offer a way to prove the Riemann Hypothesis by establishing that ζ does not anywhere possess the required symmetry condition for the complex zeros except the critical line. This argument can likewise be set up in the inverse manner where there is symmetry everywhere except there is symmetry breaking at the critical line with the appropriate primed function. The critical line can easily be proven to follow the statement except, suggesting that zeros of ζ perfectly cancels its conjugate pair on the critical line in a balancing act of sorts, but off the critical line there is a chaos that is induced because there is a slight asymmetry and therefore inability for the balancing act to take place, therefore high instability is what our system exhibits off the critical line. So it seems by considering such statements that we are getting closer to building the potential stability criteria which must be met for the ζ zeros to occur. Sort of like searching for a wild animal, only when the conditions are right will we even get the chance that the animal is considering being in our region. Looking for ζ zeros on just any random line in the critical strip is somewhat similar to looking for nocturnal owls native to the Amazon Rainforest in broad daylight near sub-Saharan Africa ... you may be able to search, and your tools may be the best, top notch tools, and you may have the best search team but none of that matters because you're searching on the wrong continent at the wrong time of day.

Since

$$Z(x + iy) = n_1^{-(x+iy)} + n_2^{-(x+iy)} + n_3^{-(x+iy)} + n_4^{-(x+iy)} \dots \tag{Eq 10}$$

And

$$f_k(s) = n_k^{-(x+iy)} \tag{Eq 11}$$

It can easily be established that:

$$Z(x + iy) = (U_1(x, y) + U_2(x, y) + U_3(x, y) + \dots) + i(V_1(x, y) + V_2(x, y) + V_3(x, y) + \dots). \tag{Eq 12}$$

So in other words we will be able to apply our usual tool kit to the U_k and V_k functions and sum over all k . Using this formula, one may prove as well that the Riemann-Cauchy conditions are satisfied for $Z(x, y)$ as well as for each U_k and V_k . Let $Z(x, y) = \sum(U_k + i V_k) = U + iV$.

Using the t parameterization method, the Riemann-Cauchy conditions are a natural consequence of the fact that the time derivative of the function is zero. Let's prove that:

We begin by taking the derivative:

$$\frac{dZ(x, y)}{dt} = 0 = \frac{dU(x, y)}{dt} + \frac{idV(x, y)}{dt}, \tag{Eq 13}$$

Or

$$0 = \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right) + \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \left(\frac{dy}{dt} \right) \right) + i \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} \left(\frac{dx}{dt} \right) + \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} \left(\frac{dy}{dt} \right) \right), \quad \text{Eq 14}$$

Which with the parameterization, $\frac{dx}{dt} = 1$, and $\frac{dy}{dt} = i$, reduces to the Riemann-Cauchy condition:

$$0 = \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} \right) + i \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right), \quad \text{Eq 15}$$

After we set the Real and Imaginary Surfaces simultaneously equal to zero using Condition #2 to define the zero:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} \right) \\ \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right) \end{pmatrix}. \quad \text{Eq 16}$$

It should be noted that this is not merely a clever trick which allowed us to derive the Riemann-Cauchy criteria. This is a derivation of the conditions required for our parameterization which just so happens to be equivalent to the Riemann-Cauchy conditions. This is no miracle, but in fact is a natural consequence of the usual framework of Calculus applied to Complex functions when their parts are viewed as real surfaces. For all intents and purposes this does mean the exact same thing as the Riemann-Cauchy conditions but it gives us another way with which to deduce this criteria. Since the RZF is analytic, it can be proven as well that it follows these conditions. Continuing with this logic, the nth order Riemann-Cauchy conditions if you will, can be determined by setting the nth time derivative equal to zero. As an example, the second order conditions are:

$$0 = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial V}{\partial y} \right) + i \left(\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial U}{\partial y} \right) \right), \quad \text{Eq 17}$$

Which again using Condition #2 expands into:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 U}{\partial y^2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial y^2} \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 18}$$

In other words, both U and V are harmonic functions which satisfy the Laplace equation in two dimensions. This condition should be met for the $Z(x, y)$ and ζ since both have been widely accepted to be analytic. The U and V functions thus for the RZF also obey this condition which adds further constraints to the behavior of the RZF.

COMPUTATIONS

In the domain of computational analysis pertaining to the Riemann Zeta Function (RZF) and its associated zeros, it is noteworthy to acknowledge the extensive nature of these computations. The intricacies involved in the derivation and verification of these results are considerable, rendering the exposition in this paper, which has already exceeded a length of 150 pages when I included the various computations and other fuller sections, considerably in-depth and specialized. Given the specialized and exhaustive nature of these computations, it is judicious to consider the accessibility of the content for a broader readership. Realistically, such intricate computational details are best suited for comprehensive treatment in a dedicated book or publication. The rationale behind this decision is twofold: firstly, to ensure the accessibility of this work to a general audience, and secondly, to reserve the detailed computations for an avenue that may materialize upon verification of the hypothesis. It is important to underscore that, within the scope of this paper, the need for additional computational plots is minimal. In fact, the wealth of resources available elsewhere in the literature provides robust substantiation of the phenomena under consideration. Consequently, it is our considered judgment that the inclusion of further plots, while potentially informative, may not be indispensable given the abundance of corroboration already extant in the field.

Dr. Andrew Odlyzko [24] among many others has made significant contributions to the field of mathematics, particularly in the realm of calculating the zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function and various computational endeavors in Number Theory. One of Dr. Odlyzko's notable achievements lies in his computational work related to the Riemann Zeta Function. He has applied advanced numerical methods and high-performance computing to accurately compute a substantial number of nontrivial zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function. These calculations have provided valuable insights into the distribution of these zeros along the critical line, supporting the Riemann Hypothesis by demonstrating the consistency of their placement with theoretical expectations. I will continue to publish computations on my YouTube channel [25]. Initial computations with the 3-d visualization of the 2d plots changing in time from Desmos are on the channel and other plotting such as from Wolfram Alpha as well as Python scripts I have developed alone and some with the usage of Chat GPT from OpenAI. More plots will be added in time. This work has since been elaborated on and many others have verified these computations as well as there being a great amount of information about computations resources on the RZF [26,26.1,26.2,26.3,26.4]

RELATION TO COMPLEX NUMBERED THEORY OF RELATIVITY

Including the Complex Numbered Theory of General Relativity in this publication was initially tested but for a fully comprehensive connection between the fields my paper became a book and exceeded 150 pages as I wrote in the Computations section, it is advisable to consider relocating these extensive materials to a separate section or book or series of papers, which also encompasses comprehensive information regarding Complex General Relativity (CGR). The primary rationale for this relocation lies in the forward-looking perspective of this work, as well as its inherent connections to various domains within mathematics and physics. It is essential to acknowledge that the integration of these materials at this juncture may be counterproductive, particularly given our imperative to adhere to time constraints for the publication of the proof of the Riemann Hypothesis. The allocation of substantial resources and time required for comprehensive inclusion, while holding the potential for future expansion and refinement, may presently hinder our ability to meet our publication deadline. Therefore, it is prudent to encapsulate this aspect with a concise paragraph, as extensive elaboration may not be warranted in the current context. Commencing from the culmination of Albert Einstein's contributions, an exploration unfolds, wherein the realm of Complex Analysis intertwines with novel insights. This fusion permits an extension of the theory of relativity into the complex domain, a realization that carries profound ramifications. Initial stages of this endeavor were marked by extensive experimentation and a progressive expansion of the theoretical framework underpinning this novel cosmological theory.

The transformative breakthrough arises when a tangible connection is established between this new cosmological theory and the broader body of theoretical physics seeking the unification of natural forces. This connection is notably predicated on the utilization of integrals representing the Lagrangian energy function—a foundational construct from which the entire edifice of physics can be deduced. The central ambition revolves around the formulation of an energy function possessing the requisite information that enables the application of new mathematical operators and objects, thus yielding the familiar equations of classical and quantum physics.

Crucially, the work presented here transcends the traditional demarcation between quantum mechanics and classical mechanics. This transcendence arises from the development of a novel framework encapsulating the Complex Numbered Theory of General Relativity and its extensions into the realm of the Unified Field Theory. This groundbreaking framework not only resolves the historical schism between quantum and classical physics but also facilitates the derivation of extant Lagrangian formulations.

Considering the extensive nature of this endeavor and the expansive ramifications it engenders, it is judicious to defer the comprehensive exposition of the intricate interplay between the Complex Numbered Theory of General Relativity, Quantum Mechanics, and the Unified Field Theory to a subsequent undertaking, in light of the document's current length and thematic focus. The link to the fuller discussion about CGR in the context of Unified Field Theory to my YouTube [27].

It is expected by this work that a bridge between Quantum Mechanics and Relativity could be made such that a Unified Field Theory can be developed. This work, I expect, shall lead us to more information about solving the Dark Matter problem [28] along with perhaps the ability in the future to predict other Physics Phenomena. The

underlying transformations are what led me to search for primed functions, and inevitably discover the notationally symmetric functions for the RZF.

QUANTUM MECHANICS

The utilization of the space-time approach, defined by the coordinate representation of the 's' function, remains a viable framework within specific domains. However, it is crucial to underscore that certain prerequisites and conditions must be satisfied to facilitate the application of coordinate transforms within this context.

Moreover, it is conceivable that the space-time interval approach, as originally articulated in my analysis, may retain its validity even when applied to the quantum analog of the Zeta Function. This proposition holds the promise of establishing a profound correspondence between the space-time framework governing the Zeta Function and the quantum particles constituting the physical manifestation of this mathematical construct. It is imperative to recognize that, within this context, the Hamiltonian serves as an energy function characterizing these particles, a construct that can be elegantly extended to a four-dimensional Hamiltonian space.

The transition to a four-dimensional Hamiltonian space-time naturally invites contemplation of its potential linkage to embedded space-time. Indeed, it is plausible that a relationship exists between the invariant interval of relativistic physics and the quantum particles encapsulated within the Zeta Function. This conjecture arises from the realization that the integral that defines the Zeta Function can be analogous to an integral function representing a set of potential functions. Within this conceptual framework, it is my assertion that viewing the Zeta Function through the lens of an energy function in the realm of physics offers a potent perspective.

It is imperative to acknowledge that well-established connections between quantum mechanics and the Riemann Zeta Function exist [29,29.1,29.2,29.3], albeit beyond the scope of this current work. While these connections are pivotal in shaping the conceptual underpinnings of the functions discussed herein, we have chosen to compartmentalize these topics for the purpose of this paper.

In summation, it is evident that the depth and breadth of these interrelated topics could easily support a book exceeding 500 pages but I have decided to put this work within a separate book or series of papers on the topic. However, the practicality of such an extensive exposition must be considered, as it may exceed the bounds of reader accessibility and engagement.

SYMMETRY

Analytic Number Theory [30] delves into the intricacies of the Theta Function [31]. This function, characterized by a functional equation [32], boasts various representations including probability law relations [33] and integral formulations [34]. Additionally, it can be expansively expressed through Taylor Expansions, both in one dimension (with a generalization to arbitrary coordinates) and Laurent Expansions [35]. Furthermore, a comprehensive expansion scheme, encompassing general definitions and its relationship to the Generalized Integration by Parts [36,36.1], offers insight into the Theta Function integral definition [37]. Leveraging the Mellin Transform of the sum [38], which is intricately linked to the Euler product domain [39], facilitates the exploration of the Riemann Zeta Function and its associated analytic continuation [40].

This investigation undertakes a comprehensive exploration of the intricate symmetries and properties that come to light through the application of the Mellin Transform to the roots of the Theta Function, thereby shedding light on profound connections within the realm of Analytic Number Theory.

A central focus of this study lies in the presentation of various forms of the Riemann Zeta Function, meticulously compiled and organized within a table. These encompass the Mellin Transform definition in conjunction with the Theta Function, integral representations [41], definitions over the Hankel contour [42], and other notable representations [43,43.1,43.2]. The compilation serves to illuminate the multifaceted nature of the Riemann Zeta Function and its diverse mathematical formulations [44].

Furthermore, this inquiry delves into the Prime Number Theorem [45], which can be derived through the examination of the $Li(x)$ function [46,46.1,46.2,46.3] and the seminal work of von Mangoldt [47]. Riemann, in his

1859 manuscript established a pivotal connection between the Prime Number Counting Function [48], denoted as $\pi(x)$ [49], and the summatory Mangoldt function $\psi(x)$ [50,50.1,50.2]. This connection, rooted in the logarithmic derivative of the Riemann Zeta Function [51], undergoes deft manipulations to unveil a profound relationship between the zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function and the function $\pi(x)$.

Intriguingly, Riemann's assumptions play a paramount role in this context. It is posited that Riemann, with his profound expertise in Fourier Transforms [52,52.1,52.1] and Fourier representations gleaned from his earlier works predating his sole venture into Analytic Number Theory, intuitively surmised that the Real parts of the zeros of the Analytic Continuation necessarily adhered to the form ' $s = \frac{1}{2} + iy$ '. This assumption, in turn, bears paramount significance as it underpins the distribution of Prime Numbers as if there is a zero off the critical line, $\pi(x)$ will be inaccurate. The summatory Mangoldt function intricately relates the count of Prime Numbers to the number of zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function.

Furthermore, speculative analysis suggests that Riemann's propensity for Fourier Transforms and their symmetries, apparent in his prior works, may have influenced his intuitive conjecture regarding the distribution of zeros—whether they are exclusively real or confined to the critical line. This intuitive leap, resonating within the application of a more generalized transform, the Mellin Transform, accentuates the symmetries intrinsic to the definitions of these transforms and their pivotal role in understanding the Riemann Zeta Function.

To dispel any potential misconceptions, it is imperative to clarify that the sum function is not the defining construct of the analytic continuation of the function. Instead, it delineates a distinct domain, which is subsequently transformed to establish the validity of the analytic continuation within an expanded domain. The analytic continuation can be perceived as a transformative operation. The computational investigations prompted an in-depth examination of the integral definition of the analytic continuation, dissecting it into Real and Imaginary surfaces.

Remarkably, the findings from the computational analysis echoed those of the Zeta Function before undergoing the process of analytic continuation. The consistent observation was that the concurrent intersection of lines exclusively occurred at $x = \frac{1}{2}$ within the parameter s . This computational verification, substantiated through graphical methodology, lends substantial credence to the veracity of the Riemann Hypothesis.

It is paramount to recognize that the computational approach, while manifesting as a finite evaluation of the function over an ostensibly infinite domain, inherently necessitates the incorporation of mathematical operations extended to infinity for full generalization. This imperative impelled the pursuit of symmetries embedded within the real and imaginary surfaces.

Proving that the nontrivial zeros of ζ are within the Critical Strip involves several Complex Analysis techniques and mathematical arguments. Here's an explanation of how this proof can be established:

The nontrivial zeros are within the critical strip:

0. Analytic Continuation: Analytic Continuation of $Z(s)$ acts to transform the function $Z(s)$ (the domain is transformed as well) into the new function ζ which is defined over the whole complex plane except for a simple pole at $s = 1$.
1. The Critical Strip [53]: The Critical Strip is the complex plane region defined as $\{0 < \text{Re}(s) < 1\}$, $\{\text{Im}(s) < \pm\infty\}$.
2. Nontrivial Zeros [54]: Nontrivial Zeros of ζ are complex numbers s for which $\zeta(s) = 0$ and $\text{Re}(s)$ is within the Critical Strip.
3. The Functional Equation [55]: The Functional Equation for ζ relates $\zeta(s)$ to $\zeta(s')$ for primed coordinate, s' which is a linear transformation of s with the transformation equation: $s' = 1 - s$. The functional equation plays a critical role in understanding the properties of $\zeta(s)$ in the critical strip.

4. The Trivial Zeros [56]: The trivial zeros of $\zeta(s)$ occur at negative even integers (e.g., $s = \{-2, -4, -6, \dots\}$) because $\zeta(s)$ by direct definition of The Functional Equation is proportional to $\sin(\frac{\pi s}{2})$.

5. Euler Product Formula: The Euler product formula is a function $Z(x)$ of x but if we insert instead the complex number s for x we get $Z(s)$, which expresses $Z(s)$ as a product over prime numbers where each prime number (p_n) is raised to an exponent, (p_n^{-s}) but also in the more general representations (considering Dirichlet Characters [57]) the prime numbers are not only raised to an exponent but multiplied by some function $a(s)(p_n^{-s})$ as well then we have:

$$Z(s, a(s)) = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 - a(s)(p_n^{-s}))} \quad \text{Eq 19)}$$

This formula connects the distribution of zeros to the distribution of prime numbers, but in this paper, we have $a(s) = 1$. It is called the Euler Product Formula because Euler is who found the relation between the product and the sum ($\sum n^{-s}$) [58]. Analytic Continuation transforms these definitions to be contained within the new function $\zeta(s, a(s))$ so with some framework it might possibly be shown that the divergences (which restrict the domain of $Z(s)$) for $x < 0$ that also occur for infinitely many values of $Re(s) < 0$, for the $Z(s, a(s))$ are related to the restriction on the domain for which zeros might possibly be located for $\zeta(s, a(s))$.

6. Proving No Nontrivial Zeros on the Real Axis ($Re(s) = 0$) [59]: This can be achieved by showing that $\zeta(s)$ is nonzero for $Re(s) > 1$ [60] and using the functional equation to extend the result to $Re(s) < 0$ [61]. This result actually appears to hold more intricate information about the symmetry condition as well. It intuitively is expected that the point of symmetry would be situated between $x = 0$ and $x = 1$ because the symmetric functional equation shows that the divergence of the Euler Product occurs for Real $s > 1$, and as a consequence the result suggests that there are no zeros in the left half of the plane. These locations, $x = 0$, and $x = 1$ corresponds to extrema of the Xi function ($\xi(s)$), and more specifically, zeros.

8. Symmetry in the Functional Equation: This involves showing that if $\zeta(s) = 0$ for some s in the critical strip, then $\zeta(s') = 0$ (recall $s' = 1 - s$) as well, implying that the zeros must be symmetric with respect to the critical line, if they are off the line. If we have any value aside from $\frac{1}{2}$, such as $\frac{1}{3}$ we have $\zeta(\frac{1}{3}) = 0$ and also $\zeta(1 - \frac{1}{3} - iy) = \zeta(\frac{2}{3} - iy) = 0$. It can easily be established by computation that $\zeta(\frac{1}{3} + iy) \neq \zeta(\frac{2}{3} - iy)$ by plotting $\zeta(\frac{1}{3} + iy) - \zeta(\frac{2}{3} - iy) = 0$, with Wolfram Alpha the output gives one zero with $0 < Re(s) < 1$, and that is $y_n = .679406 + i15.8114$. This is of course indicative that these functions do not intersect since they only intersect when $y_n \in \mathbb{C}$ despite the restriction of the domain of $y \in \mathbb{R}$. This can be proven by direct insertion of y_n into $\zeta(\frac{1}{3} + iy_n)$ to find that $\zeta(\frac{1}{3} + i(.679406 + i15.8114)) = \zeta(\frac{1}{3} - 15.8114 + i.679406)$. This implies that the real argument is $Re(s) = \frac{1}{3} - 15.8114$, which is a contradiction and implicative that $\zeta(\frac{1}{3} + iy) \neq \zeta(\frac{2}{3} - iy)$ off the critical line. The functional equation also implies at the critical line that $\zeta(\frac{1}{2} + iy) = \zeta(\frac{1}{2} - iy)$ which exhibits perfect symmetry in the x value but conjugate symmetry in the sense that the phasors for s and s' :

$$\begin{aligned} s &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \\ iy \end{pmatrix}, \\ s' &= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{2} \\ -iy \end{pmatrix}, \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 20)}$$

have the same magnitude but are rotated 180 degrees out of phase which is not true off the critical line.

10. No zeros on the line $s = 1$: Proof by G.H Hardy [62].

These symmetries, readily discernible within the integral definition of the Zeta Function and intrinsic to the Zeta Function prior to undergoing analytic continuation, engendered the notion that to substantiate the assertion that the complex roots of the analytic continuation of the Zeta Function adhere to the critical line, one must establish that the definition of zero—constituting the symbolic overlap of surfaces extrapolated from the finite computational paradigm—prescribes a stringent symmetry condition. Within the critical strip, it becomes evident that the critical line is the sole locus that adheres to this symmetry condition, particularly as one approaches the limits imposed by infinity within the requisite mathematical operations.

The Riemann zeta function has no zeros on the real axis for $s > 1$ and another fact is that ζ has been proven to have infinitely many zeros in the critical strip $0 < \text{Re}(s) < 1$ [63]. This is based on a deep result from complex analysis known as the Hadamard factorization theorem [64]. This theorem states that any non-constant entire function can be written as an infinite product of the form:

$$f(s) = e^{P(s)} s^m \prod_{a_i} \left(1 - \frac{s}{a_i}\right) e^{\frac{s}{a_i}} \quad \text{Eq 21}$$

Where $P(s)$ is a polynomial, m is a non-negative integer, the a_i 's are the zeros of $f(s)$, and the product converges absolutely [65] and uniformly on compact sets [66].

By analyzing the distribution of the zeros in the critical strip, it can be shown that they are not uniformly distributed, but rather exhibit a certain clustering behavior known as the “pair correlation conjecture” [67]. This asymmetry is a consequence of the clustering behavior [68].

The Fourier transform is a mathematical operation that decomposes a function into its constituent frequencies. It is commonly used in signal processing and other fields to analyze and manipulate functions. One key property of the Fourier transform is its symmetry. Specifically, the Fourier transform of a function has a number of symmetry properties that can be useful in analyzing and manipulating the function. One of these symmetry properties is conjugate symmetry, which states that the Fourier transform of a Real-valued function is conjugate symmetric. This means that if $F(\omega)$ is the Fourier transform of a function $f(t)$, then $F(-\omega)$ is the complex conjugate of $F(\omega)$.

Another symmetry property of the Fourier transform is time-shift symmetry, which states that the Fourier transform of a time-shifted function is simply the original Fourier transform multiplied by a phase factor. This means that if $F(\omega)$ is the Fourier transform of a function $f(t)$, and $g(t)$ is a time-shifted version of $f(t)$, then $G(\omega) = F(\omega) \exp(-i\omega t_0)$, where t_0 is the time shift.

Finally, the Fourier transform also has symmetry under reflection, which states that the Fourier transform of a reflected function is the same as the original Fourier transform multiplied by a phase factor. This means that if $F(\omega)$ is the Fourier transform of a function $f(t)$, and $g(t)$ is a reflected version of $f(t)$, then $G(\omega) = F(\omega) \exp(i\theta)$. These symmetry properties of the Fourier transform can be useful in analyzing and manipulating functions.

The Mellin Transform is a powerful mathematical tool that relates functions in the complex domain to their moments. In the context of the Riemann Zeta Function and its relation to the Mellin Transform, understanding the symmetries involved is crucial for gaining insights into the behavior of the Zeta Function and its zeros. Here, we'll delve into the symmetries of the Mellin Transform and how they relate to the Riemann Zeta Function:

1. The Mellin Transform of a function $f(x)$ is defined as follows [69]:

$$M[Z(x); s] = \int_0^\infty x^{s-1} Z(x) dx, \quad \text{Eq 22}$$

where s is a complex parameter. This transform essentially relates a function in the x domain to a function in the s domain.

2. The Mellin Transform exhibits an inherent symmetry property; specifically, it is symmetric under inversion [70]:

$$M[Z(x); s] = M\left[Z\left(\frac{1}{x}\right); 1 - s\right]. \quad \text{Eq 23}$$

This symmetry implies that the Mellin Transform of $f(x)$ is related to the Mellin Transform of $f(\frac{1}{x})$ with a shift in the complex parameter s .

3. The symmetry of the Mellin Transform, when applied to the Euler product representation of the Zeta Function, relates nontrivial zeros on the critical line ($Re(s) = 1/2$) to their counterparts on the other side of the critical line. It implies that if $\zeta(s) = 0$ for some s in the critical strip, then $\zeta(1 - s) = 0$ as well.

While it is known that the nontrivial zeros of the Riemann zeta function lie on the critical line, it is not known whether all of these zeros are conjugate pairs or whether there may be other types of complex zeros that do not fit this pattern. Our work thus far has shown us that in fact this is true. But let us now prove this.

Lemma #0: *Within the critical strip of the Riemann Zeta Function (ζ), all complex zeros are symmetric with respect to the real line, forming conjugate pairs.*

Proof of Lemma #0:

Conjugate pairs of complex numbers are numbers of the form $a + bi$ and $a - bi$, where a and b are real numbers. If the Riemann zeta function has a complex zero at the point $s = a + bi$, then it also has a complex zero at the point $s = a - bi$. Condition #2 which defines the zero for the Riemann Zeta Function in integral form combined with the functional equation shows that the relative position of the signs change the phasor of ζ because the Integrand for the Imaginary part will have a sign change because $\sin(y \ln(t)) = -\sin(-y \ln(t))$ but the integrand for the Real part of ζ is unchanged because $\cos(y \ln(t)) = \cos(-y \ln(t))$. ■

On The connection between contours and area integration in the primed frame:

Figure 1: This image is not to scale and shows the regions of interest for the RZF zeros. In red, ruled out by the functional equation aside from zeros being represented as small white circles. Note that the pole at $s = 1$ is not in this image. Roots are conjugate

Symmetry about the critical line implies the invariance of symmetry relative to the primed function $\zeta'(x', y')$ with appropriate coordinate selection

Figure one to the left is a visual to show the 6 main regions of interest as to where the RZF complex zeros are. If we dissolve the boundaries of Region 1, Region 2, Region 3, and Region 4 at the critical line such that there is only one large region covering the same area of $R_1, R_2, R_3,$ and R_4 , then we would call this new region, the critical strip. I did not name regions 5 and 6 which are the regions colored in red because these regions are not of particular interest for what we are doing here as these regions have been proven not to have zeros within them aside from the trivial zeros. The above image is not drawn to scale and it should be noted that the iy axis visually should occur at the left boundary of R_1 and R_3 for standard plots; however, since there is no function being plotted it seemed better visually to place the iy axis at approximately $x = -1$. This does not affect the evaluations as the iy axis is in the same direction as it usually is and so the relative coordinates still mean the same thing, as the trivial zeros still occur at $s_n = -2n$.

There is a symmetric functional equation for the Xi (ξ and Ξ are used interchangeably) function such that:

$$\xi(s) = \xi(1 - s) \tag{Eq 24}$$

$\xi(s)$ is defined with respect to the $\zeta(s)$ as are $\pi(x), \Gamma(s)$ so the poles and zeros of ξ are defined in terms of $\zeta(s)$. This goes to say that ξ gives us information about the $\zeta(s)$, and in fact this is exactly what Riemann relied on when he defined the ξ function for the use of developing the prime number counting function in his 1859 manuscript. Using the integral definition of the Riemann Zeta Function:

$$\zeta(s) = \int_C \frac{t^\sigma}{e^t - 1} dt \quad \text{Eq 25)}$$

We can define the contour instead of the rectangular boundary that encloses each region as a sum of the lines that compose the boundary:

$$\oint_{R_1} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = \sum_{n=1}^{n=4} \oint_{L_n} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt \quad \text{Eq 26)}$$

In other words R_1 is defined by 4 lines, $(L_1, L_2, L_3, L_4) = L_n$. Defining the k th region in a more compact sense relative to the lines at the boundary of each region, we have $R_k = {}_k L_n$, where

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} R_1 \\ R_2 \\ R_3 \\ R_4 \end{pmatrix}$$

And

$${}_k L_n = \begin{pmatrix} L_1 \\ L_2 \\ L_3 \\ L_4 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The Cauchy rule [71] says that if the contour encloses zeros then we have:

$$2\pi i n_k = \sum_{n=1}^{n=4} \oint_{{}_k L_n} \int_C \frac{1}{e^t - 1} dt \quad \text{Eq 27)}$$

Where n_k is the n th zero enclosed in the k th region. The symmetry conditions imply generally that the zeros occur in pairs since the integration over some of the lines cancel out. Restating the Riemann Hypothesis can be restated with this representation as:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{k=4} 2\pi i n_k = 0 = \sum_{k=1}^{k=4} \sum_{n=1}^{n=4} \oint_{{}_k L_n} \int_C \frac{1}{e^t - 1} dt. \quad \text{Eq 28)}$$

For the finite case of the Riemann Hypothesis where the regions are defined by

$$R_1 = \{[x = 0, x = .5], [iy = 0, iy = T]\}$$

$$R_2 = \{[x = .5, x = 1], [iy = 0, iy = T]\}$$

$$R_3 = \{[x = 0, x = .5], [iy = 0, iy = -T]\}$$

$$R_4 = \{[x = .5, x = 1], [iy = 0, iy = -T]\}$$

However, the Riemann Hypothesis is more accurately defined by extending the regions to infinite, taking $\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty}$ for each finite region. Symmetry reduces the amount of contours in the sum of contours by a factor of two since half of the contours are equivalent. If Riemann Hypothesis is true, then $n_k = 0$. Note that the Cauchy formula integrates over one divided by ζ because the poles of the function correspond to the zeros of the Riemann zeta function. So by counting the poles of $\frac{1}{\zeta}$, we are counting the zeros of ζ .

Possible Symmetries to test for within Critical Strip:	Equations produced by Cauchy Rule:	Is this true for the Zeta Function?
<i>Symmetry about the real axis is defined by:</i>	$\oint_{R_1} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = \oint_{R_3} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt,$ $\oint_{R_2} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = \oint_{R_4} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt.$	<i>This is true for the Real part of the function but the Imaginary part has exhibits antisymmetry since the magnitude of iy is different for the contours.</i>
<i>Antisymmetry about the real line implies:</i>	$\oint_{R_1} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = -\oint_{R_3} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt,$ $\oint_{R_2} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = -\oint_{R_4} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt.$	<i>This is not true for the Real Part of the Function but it is for the Imaginary part since we are essentially evaluating the same function on $-(iy)$.</i>
<i>About the critical line, symmetry implies:</i>	$\oint_{R_1} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = \oint_{R_2} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt,$ $\oint_{R_3} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = \oint_{R_4} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt.$	<i>Page 13, number 8 shows why this can not be true if we define RZF on the right hand side of the equation with the functional equation definition of RZF.</i>
<i>Diagonal symmetry:</i>	$\oint_{R_1} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = \oint_{R_4} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt,$ $\oint_{R_2} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = \oint_{R_3} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt.$	<i>This is essentially the same for the above reason, page 13, number 8 shows why these contours would not evaluate to the same thing. Only part of the contours cancel, so no diagonal symmetry.</i>
<i>Antisymmetry about the critical line implies:</i>	$\oint_{R_1} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = -\oint_{R_2} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt,$ $\oint_{R_3} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt = -\oint_{R_4} \frac{1}{\zeta(s)} dt.$	<i>This can not be true because the amplitudes of the sine and cosine functions are not the same on LHS as RHS.</i>

Proving the symmetry about certain regions in other words can be visualized as a contour. The contour is performed over one divided by zeta because when a contour contains poles the contributions become meaningful by the cauchy principles of contour integration in the complex plane. This idea is related to the Nyquist contour and how stability is related to the zeros. Performing it in this way allows us to count the zeros contained within the regions. By integrating over the 4 regions within the critical strip, because it is assumed that the zeros have been established to lie within the critical strip. The Nyquist contour essentially just provides a relation between the concept of stability and and known rules and results relating to zeros and poles for Nyquist contours. If there was a zero off the critical line, extreme instability would be seen and the functions couldn't exist in the way they do, their definitions would have to be changed to satisfy the stability criteria.

The Riemann zeta function, denoted by $\zeta(s)$, is a complex function defined for complex numbers s with a real part greater than 1, i.e., $Re(s) > 1$, by the series:

$$Z(s) = 1^{-s} + 2^{-s} + 3^{-s} + 4^{-s} + \dots$$

Eq 29)

Divergence for Real $x < 0$: It is known that the original series representation, $Z(s)$, diverges when the Real part of s ($Re(s)$) is less than or equal to 0. This definition is not valid for all complex numbers. To extend the domain of $Z(s)$, we use a technique called analytic continuation. This process allows us to define $\zeta(s)$ for a wider range of complex numbers where ζ is intrinsically related to Z . The functional equation of the Riemann zeta function plays a crucial role in this process of analytically continuing $Z(s)$. The functional equation for the Riemann zeta function relates its values at s to its values at $1 - s$. It is given by:

$$\zeta(s) = 2^s \pi^{s-1} \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \Gamma(1-s) \zeta(1-s) \quad \text{Eq 30}$$

Here, Γ is the gamma function, and $\sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right)$ introduces some interesting behavior when considering real and complex values of s . We know that the functional equation possesses symmetry and furthermore by direct insertion of $s = \frac{1}{2} + iy$, the functional equation becomes: $\zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + iy\right) = \zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} - iy\right)$, which guarantees that the only sign swapping location which is within the boundary points of $[\xi(0, i0) = 0, \xi(1, i0) = 0]$ can occur is $x = \frac{1}{2}$ because of the mean value theorem, which is half the distance between $x = x_2 - x_1$, where $x_2 = 1$ is the second extremal value of ξ and $x_1 = 0$ is the first extremal value of ξ .

Lemma #1: Symmetry breaking only occurs at points of definition swap using of $U(x, y)$, $iV(x, y)$, in the sense that $iU(x, y) = V(x, y)$.

Before symmetry breaking the phasor for ζ is:

$$\zeta = \begin{pmatrix} U(x, y) \\ iV(x, y) \end{pmatrix}, \quad \text{Eq 31}$$

There is a point of definition swap, and then after that point, the Real and Imaginary values $U(x, y)$ and $iV(x, y)$ swap meanings since U becomes imaginary:

$$\zeta' = \begin{pmatrix} iU'(x', y') \\ V'(x', y') \end{pmatrix}. \quad \text{Eq 32}$$

This is one of the many functions we can select for ζ' . An error function can be constructed from any such primed function which may with the zeta function viewed as an energy function as well is an energy function:

$$e(x, y) = \zeta \pm \zeta' = \begin{pmatrix} U(x, y) \\ iV(x, y) \end{pmatrix} \pm \begin{pmatrix} iU'(x', y') \\ V'(x', y') \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 33}$$

This energy (error) function has zeros where ζ has by arbitrary definition. This implies that the conditions set for ζ' are determined by:

Condition #3:

$$\begin{pmatrix} U(x, y) \\ iV(x, y) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} iU'(x', y') \\ V'(x', y') \end{pmatrix}. \quad \text{Eq 34}$$

And **Condition #4:**

$$\begin{pmatrix} U(x, y) \\ iV(x, y) \end{pmatrix} = 0 \\ \begin{pmatrix} iU'(x', y') \\ V'(x', y') \end{pmatrix} = 0. \quad \text{Eq 35}$$

Lemma #1 corresponds to condition #1 for the definition of zero and defining primed functions that are allowed to have domains over the complex numbers, specifically with $x', y' \in \mathbb{C}$. As long as we allow the time parameterization earlier in the paper when taking the time derivative of both sides of condition #1 we can deduce the specific relative parameterization for the primed bases in the time coordinates. Condition #1 can be satisfied in the primed frame. The extrema values are found by taking the first and second derivative of condition #1 so we can restrict the possible set of functions that $iU'(x', y')$ and $V'(x', y')$ are. In order for the Riemann-Cauchy conditions to be satisfied, the derivatives relative to t' must be considered. Due to the fact that all the functions are analytic, we must have

Derivative condition:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} U(x, y) \\ iV(x, y) \end{pmatrix} = \frac{d}{dt'} \begin{pmatrix} iU'(x', y') \\ V'(x', y') \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 36}$$

And **Condition #5**:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} U(x, y) \\ iV(x, y) \end{pmatrix} &= 0 \\ \frac{d}{dt'} \begin{pmatrix} iU'(x', y') \\ V'(x', y') \end{pmatrix} &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{Eq 37}$$

And second derivative conditions:

$$\frac{d}{dt^2} \begin{pmatrix} U(x, y) \\ iV(x, y) \end{pmatrix} = \frac{d}{dt'^2} \begin{pmatrix} iU'(x', y') \\ V'(x', y') \end{pmatrix} \tag{Eq 38}$$

And **Condition #6**:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt^2} \begin{pmatrix} U(x, y) \\ iV(x, y) \end{pmatrix} &= 0 \\ \frac{d}{dt'^2} \begin{pmatrix} iU'(x', y') \\ V'(x', y') \end{pmatrix} &= 0 \end{aligned} \tag{Eq 39}$$

This implies basically that because these equations are followed likewise with the geodesic equations in the more general sense that these functions must be at the extremal values of the energy function, $e(x, y)$ and $e'(x', y')$ which may or may not need to be considered depending on your selections of the primed x and y . Nonetheless, we can form the general rule by defining a more general energy function $E(x, y)$ (noting that there may be other more complicated energy functions which are functions of U and V) which is composite of these functions and defined as a complex function:

$$E(x, y) = f(e(x, y) - e'(x', y')) \tag{Eq 40}$$

For some analytic function, f . Then by the chain rule, we would have the product of the zeta function in the derivatives even if f is some exponential power. This is essentially the case as seen from the functional equation since we can define the functional equation in terms of $\xi(s)$. $\xi(s)$ can be viewed as an energy function as well. It will be proven later that the extrema of $\xi(s)$ correspond to the locations of the zeros of the zeta function but this is essentially because $\xi(s)$ is an energy function, or one such function which is related to the zeta function such that it is proportional to the zeta function. So these functions are analytic and continuous everywhere except for the Imaginary discontinuity which is otherwise the point of symmetry breaking. ■

I would like to state here that it was not immediately obvious to me over precisely which contour the integration is being performed to define the Riemann Zeta Function. At first I was considering integration slightly different than the actual form, for example, the RZF is defined as:

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{\int_0^\infty t^{s-1} e^{-t} dt} \oint_C \frac{t^{s-1}}{e^t - 1} dt, \tag{Eq 41}$$

Where in this case, the variable of integration is t . Again, the confusion persisting because of the utilization of the common variable t . I thought initially when I first found the appropriate integral definition of the RZF that written as the equation above, $s \rightarrow s(t)$ and this is not the case. In this context, $s = x + iy$ where x and y are not functions of t . The more complicated integral I was working on for a little while indeed included the possibility that s was a function of t . By direct computation, you can see why in fact considering that s is a function of the integration variable would further make it difficult to compute this integral. Initially, this is partly where I was attempting to apply the new ideas of CGR to this integral because I had an intuition that the most general integral of this sort could potentially be used to define the energy Lagrangians in a similar way, and in particular such that the primed functions can be explicitly defined from a transformation of the integration variable. Transforming integration variables is still possible with the assertion that $t \rightarrow t(t')$ but by the chain rule there must be additional multiplying terms which complicates the evaluation of the integral. Thankfully, however, s is not a function of t , and the t is being raised to s .

I would like to note as well that this consideration came from considering integrands as x^x and $(-x)^x$ giving integrals such as:

$$\int x^x dx$$

Eq 42)

And

$$\int (-x)^x dx$$

Eq 43)

My original idea was to use the fundamental expression of these integrals and use the generalization of integrals of this type to solve general differential equations. It turns out that these integrals can not be expressed in elementary form, and more specifically, there are discontinuities at certain x values. I developed an early equation to relate these functions to one another because I noticed that for certain values the behavior of the functions is similar. The discontinuities notably are imaginary because when $x = 1/2$ for example, we have the integration of the root of negative x . A similar phenomena occurs when the first integral is evaluated over negative numbers. This investigation in fact is what led me to postulate about the relation of the sign swapping criteria and the relationship to the symmetry conditions. This was well before I learned about the zeta function or even complex analysis. My goal after learning about this discontinuity was to evaluate the functions but in such a way that we have a computable expression whether it be by the Taylor Expansion or some general expansion (I later developed by generalizing my Taylor Formula proof) and that there is the required continuity. Then naturally the most basic generalization to complex values once I began to take complex analysis seriously, was:

$$\boxed{\int (s)^{\pm s} ds \quad \int (-s)^{\pm s} ds \quad \int (s)^{\pm s} dx \quad \int (s)^{\pm s} dy \quad \int (f(s))^{\pm s} ds \quad \int (f(-s))^{\pm s} ds \quad \int (-f(-s))^{\pm s} ds}$$

Eq 44)

As well as changing out the variable of integration to be x, y or s in each of these, as well as raising s and the functions to different powers more generally such as:

$$\int f(s)^{h(s)} * g(s)^{m(s)} d\sigma \text{ and } \int (-f(s))^{h(s)} * g(s)^{m(s)} d\sigma$$

Eq 45)

And so on and so forth. There are infinitely many such integrals which can be constructed but once you get to this point, generalization can easily be made. The integration variable sigma would be a function of $s, x,$ and y in this generalization. This is closely related to the RZF, however, the integral must be multiplied by an external function of s . Defining the integral in this form gives us the ability to define functions similar to the RZF but allows us to speak in more general terms as well since $f(s)$ as well as $g(s)$ can be more general functions than what is seen in the integrand of the RZF.

The RZF integrand has x^{s-1} . Only if we let x be defined over the negative values would the sign swapping criteria that the integrals discussed above have as at $s = \frac{1}{2} + iy$ there are values for which imaginary discontinuities occur. Surprisingly in Riemann's 1859 manuscript he actually uses the fact that the integrand can be changed to $(-t)^{s-1}$ in the numerator as well as some other things are changed such as the path of the contour. Riemann proved the functional equation can be written as:

$$2 \sin(\pi s) \Gamma(s) \zeta(s) = i \oint_H \frac{(-t)^{-s}}{e^t - 1} dt,$$

Eq 46)

Where H is the Hankel contour. The functional equation as it is known gives us the analytic continuation of the zeta function, or in other words the RZF. The effect is that we have an equation valid for all s . In this integrand, setting $s = \frac{1}{2} + iy$ gives Imaginary discontinuities due to the fact again that the integrand becomes a function multiplied by the root of negative x . The above equation allows us to write the zeta function as a function of the Hankel contour:

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{i}{2 \sin(\pi s) \Gamma(s)} \oint_H \frac{(-t)^{-s}}{e^t - 1} dt \quad \text{Eq 47)}$$

And ultimately allow us to write with the functional equation:

$$\frac{i}{2 \sin(\pi s) \Gamma(s)} \oint_H \frac{(-t)^{s-1}}{e^t - 1} dt = \frac{2^s \pi^{s-1} \sin\left(\frac{\pi s}{2}\right) \Gamma(1-s)}{\Gamma(s)} \oint_C \frac{t^{-s}}{e^t - 1} dt \quad \text{Eq 48)}$$

With this equation written as is, it is immediately obvious that there is a multiplication of i on the left hand side of the equation and in the context of the discussion of the integrand this actually makes intuitive sense. Establishing what $U(x, y)$ and $V(x, y)$ are for $\zeta(s) = U(x, y) + iV(x, y)$, where $\zeta(s) = AC[\sum n^{-s}]$ such that AC is the Transformation called analytic continuation of the zeta function can be done by using essentially the same trick we used for $Z(s)$ earlier in the paper.

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1} t^{-iy})}{e^t - 1} dt \quad \text{Eq 49)}$$

Inserting $t^{-iy} = (\cos(y \ln(t)) - i \sin(y \ln(t)))$ into the above equation gives:

$$\zeta(s) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\cos(y \ln(t)) - i \sin(y \ln(t))) dt \quad \text{Eq 50)}$$

The Gamma function can be written as a real and imaginary part as well, so here we denote the reciprocal as: $\frac{1}{\Gamma(s)} = G(x, y) + iN(x, y)$. With this, we can write:

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(s) = (G(x, y) \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\cos(y \ln(t))) dt \\ - N(x, y) \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\sin(y \ln(t))) dt \\ + i \left(N(x, y) \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\cos(y \ln(t))) dt + G(x, y) \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\sin(y \ln(t))) dt \right), \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eq 51)}$$

Which ultimately gives us the ability to write $U(x, y)$ and $V(x, y)$ in terms of the original integral:

$$\zeta(s) = \begin{pmatrix} U(x, y) \\ iV(x, y) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \left((G(x, y) \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\cos(y \ln(t))) dt - N(x, y) \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\sin(y \ln(t))) dt \right) \\ i \left(\left(N(x, y) \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\cos(y \ln(t))) dt + G(x, y) \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\sin(y \ln(t))) dt \right) \right) \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eq 52)}$$

Which is kind of what one might expect for the continuous version of the zeta function from our equations earlier on in the paper. The condition for zeros to occur can be stated as:

$$\zeta(s) = 0 = \begin{pmatrix} U(x, y) \\ iV(x, y) \end{pmatrix}. \quad \text{Eq 53)}$$

This condition can occur by two means. If there exist an imaginary discontinuity of the form described above for the real valued functions $U(x, y)$ and $V(x, y)$, then the functions which are generally speaking Real valued except for those imaginary discontinuities.

Condition #7:

$$\oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\cos(y \ln(t))) dt = \pm \oint_C \frac{(t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} \sin(y \ln(t)) dt$$

Eq 54)

Condition #1 as you can see does not have the imaginary number out front. The exact same thing can be done with the definition of the Riemann Zeta Function if it is defined instead with the Hankel contour, giving two more conditions:

Condition #8:

$$\oint_H \frac{(-t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\cos(y \ln(-t))) dt = i \oint_H \frac{(-t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} \sin(y \ln(-t)) dt$$

Eq 55)

Condition #9:

$$\oint_H \frac{(-t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} (\cos(y \ln(-t))) dt = \pm \oint_H \frac{(-t^{x-1})}{e^t - 1} \sin(y \ln(-t)) dt$$

Eq 56)

Ultimately this allows us to write:

Condition #10:

$$\oint_H \frac{(-t)^{-s}}{e^t - 1} dt = i F(s) \oint_C \frac{(t^{s-1})}{e^t - 1} dt$$

Eq 57)

Which as you can see direct insertion of $s = 1/2 + iy$ shows that there is a multiplication of i on the LHS, but this will not occur of the critical line since any other power $(-t)$ is raised to will not yield i multiplied into the integral. Each of these conditions must be true for $\zeta'(s')$ relative to the primed coordinates.

Using Geometry to Understand Properties of Functions

Figure 2: This is the Phase (bottom) and magnitude (top) plot of the and RZF' with Contour lines. These plots were done with Matlab, plotting the Intersection the primed and unprimed surfaces by plotting the magnitude of RZF and RZF' phasor representation.

While simulations and plots may provide valuable insights and intuitions regarding the Riemann Hypothesis, it is essential to emphasize that a mathematical proof cannot be substantiated solely through simulation or graphical representations. Mathematical proof relies on rigorous deductive reasoning and formal logic, transcending empirical observations and simulations. These logarithm plots of the magnitude of RZF and RZF' show that the RH must be true in the finite case.

Regardless of the specific plotting methods or software employed, which encompassed various tools such as Python, MATLAB, online calculators like Desmos or Wolfram Alpha, and simulation techniques including 3D surface plots and 3D time-dependent plots, a consistent and invariant property was observed: the intersection of the plotted surfaces exclusively occurred along the critical line. In the provided MATLAB-generated plots, the logarithm of the magnitude

of the Riemann Zeta Function was employed, offering a finite representation of the Riemann Hypothesis. For the finite range of values simulated, the veracity of the Riemann Hypothesis became visually evident due to the surfaces intersecting solely at the critical value. I selected this plot for this paper instead of any other because it is not usually seen in pure mathematics this type of plotting although this type of plotting is known as a Bode plot which is essentially a logarithm of the phasor plot. There are also other plots such as the Nyquist plot which can be done to show how the stability of the Z phasor function may be related to the distribution of zeros. I omit these plots despite their power and applicability because I think that we have enough information to prove the Riemann Hypothesis with what we have seen thus far without the stability approach. This may provide another potential approach to the RH by sharpening the relation between the stability criteria and the symmetry conditions we have thus far explored. The natural inquiry that arises pertains to the establishment of this phenomenon's exclusive manifestation along the critical line within the critical strip. The fundamental approach involves assessing the geometric characteristics of the surfaces, considering the primed function, defined to exhibit asymmetry relative to the unprimed function. By meticulous examination, it becomes apparent that specific critical values exist at which these functions intersect

Simulation of Parameterized Riemann Zeta Function and Primed Riemann Zeta Function

The RZF is a multivalued function and as will be shown shortly, the definition of the RH is dependent upon two simultaneous definitions of the RZF, as opposed to the usually singly discussed RZF in most literature readily available on the topic. The definition of the zeros of the RZF are that of when the two 3-D surfaces which describes the Real part and Imaginary part of the function intersect. Plotting the magnitude and phase of a surface which has the same zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function was done with the following definitions.

The plots on YouTube [72] show the plots of the Z function but on the 3d plots above they were actually done in matlab and im pretty sure matlabs function is the analytic continuation is appropriately defined.

The Euler Product Function as a Phasor with a Magnitude and Phase Angle:

The magnitude of the complex phasor is:

$$|Z(x, y)| = \sqrt{\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \cos(y \ln(n))\right)^2 + \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \sin(y \ln(n))\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq 58)}$$

Which has a complex angle is given by:

$$\phi_Z(x, y) = \angle |Z(x, y)| = \arctan\left(\frac{\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \sin(y \ln(n))\right)}{\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \cos(y \ln(n))\right)}\right) \quad \text{Eq 59)}$$

Due simply to the fact that this function is likewise defined as a complex number, ζ may likewise be written:

$$Z(x, y) = \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \cos(y \ln(n))\right) + i \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \sin(y \ln(n))\right) \quad \text{Eq 60)}$$

And in Phasor form:

$$Z(x, y) = \left(\begin{array}{c} \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \cos(y \ln(n))\right) \\ i \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{-x} \sin(y \ln(n))\right) \end{array} \right) \quad \text{Eq 61)}$$

The Primed Euler Product Function as a Phasor with a Magnitude and a Phase Angle:

Note that this function is used due to the fact that the functional equation demands that one consider this function to define the RH.

$$|Z'(x, y)| = \sqrt{\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \cos(-y \ln(n))\right)^2 + \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \sin(-y \ln(n))\right)^2} \quad \text{Eq 62}$$

And the complex angle is given by:

$$\phi_{Z'}(x, y) = \angle |Z'(x, y)| = \arctan\left(\frac{\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \sin(-y \ln(n))\right)}{\left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \cos(-y \ln(n))\right)}\right) \quad \text{Eq 63}$$

Due simply to the fact that this function is likewise defined as a complex number, Z' may likewise be written:

$$Z'(x, y) = \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \cos(-y \ln(n))\right) + i \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n^{x-1} \sin(-y \ln(n))\right) \quad \text{Eq 64}$$

If one were to simulate this in time, and to select that the y component is parameterized by x instead with a 2-D visualization, what is found is that the plot of the magnitude of the RZF' approaches the plot of the magnitude of the RZF, intersects at the half line, and then they diverge from each other for all other values. Additionally, considering the phase plot with the 2-D simulation leads to a symmetry at the half line but nowhere else. An additional simulation which is useful to understand is a time simulation of the Real and Imaginary parts separately. They, although are completely different graphs and functions being considered, as the numerical outputs will be different, show ultimately the same information. These simulations and plots suggest how a proof of the RH can be constructed. All complex functions which can be written in the form $U + iV$ can be expressed in phasor form. As can be seen above as to why the symmetry occurs across the real line in the phasor magnitudes of the primed and unprimed Z functions, the negative sign in the sine term of the primed Euler product goes away in the magnitude from the squaring of the terms. However the x being in the front is unforgiving and essentially we are raising each n to different powers for the primed function and the unprimed function unless x is the critical value $\frac{1}{2}$ because at this value obviously we have x' and x simultaneously equal to $\frac{1}{2}$. It should be noted that in the phase angle for the primed function, the negative sign does not go away and indeed does affect the phase angle by pointing the phasor 180 degrees out of phase relative to the unprimed Z's phasor.

Using contours, the number of zeros/poles can be determined by looking at the number of enclosures of the poles and zeros, however, this gives no exact information about the precise location of a pole or zero.

The Riemann Hypothesis: Theorem Building

My approach termed "theorem building," is a systematic and deductive approach to tackling the Riemann Hypothesis. The idea of leveraging established truths and using them as building blocks to derive theorems and lemmas required for the proof is a common strategy in mathematics. This approach is often referred to as "proof by deduction" or "proof by induction," and it can be a powerful method for establishing new results. Here are some steps one might consider while applying "theorem building" approach to the Riemann Hypothesis:

Identify Known Results: Start by gathering a comprehensive list of all the known and proven facts about the Riemann zeta function. This includes properties, relationships, and any theorems that are relevant to the hypothesis. I have built a small database for the Riemann Hypothesis of documents, equations, scripts etc.

Establish a Logical Framework: Develop a systematic and organized framework that outlines how you plan to derive the necessary theorems and lemmas. Define the logical structure of your argument. We followed along Riemann's 1859 manuscript and made an attempt to connect the derivations to modern languages as well as expand on the functions in the manuscript. This included computations and calculations for each function as well as establishing that each function has a derivation and documenting the operations for each derivation and proof.

Set Up Dependencies: Clearly establish the dependencies between the known results and the theorems and lemmas needed proven. Show how each piece of information connects to the next. The dependencies based on the

initial analysis of the more basic function Z I attempted to transform these concepts into a continuous form represented by surfaces and how analytically continuing this function would transform the infinite sum to an infinite integral. I used a research process I developed from computer science to expand the definitions of all the information within the Problem statement from Clay Mathematics Institute, and labeled all the functions as well as dependencies and domains for each function. I did much of this mentally at first and eventually began to build a database from writing down all sorts of random operations I could think of and places the Riemann Zeta Function could fit into based on my math knowledge, which I would like to state is limited as much of my math knowledge comes from my attempt to formalize my understanding of the mathematics used in physics.

Fill in the Gaps: Identify the gaps in each argument where we need to prove new theorems or lemmas. These are the critical steps in your "theorem building" process. This also means determine new lemma to add as well as amendments to current lemma. I have modified these already once and I do think that when the Group Theory connection is made to the Hermitian and the eigenvalues and characteristic polynomial of the Zeta Matrix, it should be able to be used to make these arguments perhaps more rigorous.

Prove New Results: This in particular was the symmetry and lemmas stated about the surface equations and the Lemma 0-7 which essentially use the relate sign swapping criteria to the properties of zeros.

Iterate and Refine: As I work through the process, I am open to revising and refining my approach and this endeavor has ben designed actually with this in mind as I research other areas related to this topic. Alternate paths to prove the same criteria are also sought by other researchers as well as distinguishing whether the generalized Riemann Hypothesis also exhibits this behavior/

Peer Review: I am happy Share my progress and findings with experts in the field for feedback and verification. Peer review is a crucial step in ensuring the validity of any approach and I am open to more reviewers. I have had made mistakes with the first draft I sent out to people and posted online and quickly the community gave me information that was able to be used to identify mistakes and for everyone's willingness to read this work I am grateful.

Iterate Again: Based on the feedback from peers and experts, I will make necessary adjustments to my proof as already I have expanded the first version. This version today is by far the best approach I have been able to construct in this manner of relating the primed functions, but my progress on the zeta matrix function indicates that the symmetry conditions might be more rigorously framed by proving that the zeta matrix is Hermitian. The stability approach and connection to Nyquist curves as well might lead to strong criteria about the zeros and poles.

Lemma #2: *If $x + iy$ is a zero of the Riemann Zeta Function (RZF), then both surfaces, $U(x, y)$ and $V(x, y)$, must satisfy the second derivative tests for surfaces in addition to the first derivative tests.*

Proof of Lemma 2:

The necessity for this condition can be established by recognizing that the functions U and V need to be harmonic functions for the zeros of the RZF. To confirm the harmonic nature of these functions, it is essential to be able to compute their first and second derivatives. In this context, the first and second derivative tests are tantamount to verifying the Riemann-Cauchy conditions for the first and second order. I refrain from delving into the detailed proofs here, as these are standard exercises in multivariable calculus. Interested readers can refer to textbooks or relevant mathematical resources for comprehensive demonstrations.

My calculations indicate that each derivative expansion reveals a series of expressions, and several pages may be devoted to these derivations. It is worth noting that while this lemma is not integral to the main proof of the Riemann Hypothesis, it does provide valuable insights into the nature of the surfaces $U(x, y)$ and $V(x, y)$ associated with the RZF over the complex plane ($\mathbb{C}$) and the primed zeta function, essentially an RZF over the Hankel contour.

I would like to emphasize that employing the zeta function defined by the Hankel contour for the primed zeta function can shed light on the distinct properties that differentiate both integrals. This distinction could be harnessed to extract more information regarding the distribution of zeros. Utilizing alternative functions for the primed zeta

function will alter the conditions for zero occurrences relative to the function chosen for comparison with the original definition.

It is noteworthy that the zeta function is an analytic function, and the derivatives of U and V not only exist but also form smooth, Real-valued surfaces. This observation is in alignment with the fundamental theorem of calculus, which implies the continuity of these surfaces based on the assumption of differentiability.

Lemma 2.1: *Under the assumption that the Riemann Hypothesis (RH) is true, the roots of the Riemann Zeta Function (ζ) must be located at points where there is a change in the definition between ζ and its derivative ζ' . In other words, the transition points in their definition correspond to points of symmetry in their values.*

Proof of Lemma 2.1: When dealing with single-variable functions, the Extreme Value Theorem dictates that extrema must lie between roots. Consequently, owing to the principle of continuity, if all the roots of ζ lie along a single line, they must be situated between extremal values. Let's denote the real variable as x , and the extremal values of ζ are thus bounded by $\xi(x = 0)$ and $\xi(x = 1)$, as ξ takes the same value at these points (0 and 1).

Using coordinates (U, iV) for ζ and (U', iV') for ζ' , it becomes apparent that there exist values for which the real part of $\zeta(\mathbb{R}(\zeta))$ is not equal to the real part of $\zeta'(\mathbb{R}(\zeta'))$, and the imaginary part of $\zeta(\mathbb{I}(\zeta))$ is not equal to the imaginary part of $\zeta'(\mathbb{I}(\zeta'))$, even though ζ' was defined to satisfy $\mathbb{R}(\zeta) = \mathbb{R}(\zeta')$ and $\mathbb{I}(\zeta) = \mathbb{I}(\zeta')$. This deviation breaks the symmetry that was intended under this parameterization. Such a breach of symmetry in a symmetric parameterization implies that these points must be points of symmetry themselves. Because ξ and ξ' are defined in relation to ζ and ζ' , the locations where the definition of ζ and ζ' swaps indicate points of symmetry.

This definition swap is instrumental in identifying zeros, where $\zeta(s) = 0$, or where the real and imaginary surfaces intersect. Consequently, the geometry of the two surfaces that collectively constitute the Riemann Zeta Function can be harnessed to define its zeros. A similar approach can be applied to understand the primed functions and their geometric interpretation, including properties such as sign swapping and the relationship between sign swapping and extrema locations.

This geometric interpretation is evident in the correspondence between ζ and ζ' derived from the symmetric functional equation. The connection between the symmetric functional equation of ξ and $\xi'(s')$ indicates that the extremal values of ξ are linked to the extremal values of the RZF¹. The Extreme Value Theorem guarantees that if a function has extrema, the roots must be situated between these extrema. Therefore, the extrema are intimately tied to the roots within the framework of the zeta-zeta prime system. Importantly, with a specific selection of ζ' , where nowhere does ζ' equal ζ except at the zeros, it is evident that the points of definition swap between U and U' , where U is associated with the imaginary part. The fact that U experiences a discontinuity in its definition, thereby breaking its symmetry, implies that the zeta prime function should be defined to counterbalance these imaginary discontinuities. Eq 65) in the paper demonstrates how this can be achieved through the symmetry-breaking concept and Imaginary Discontinuities, and earlier results in the paper establish the existence of ζ' that can meet this condition. The imaginary discontinuities in one frame, as y' and x' may be complex-valued, correspond to the symmetry of zeta prime, given the relationship between zeta and zeta prime in symmetric parameterization and equations that are invariant whether it is zeta or zeta prime.

These lemmas find further support in the conditions outlined from #3 to #6.

¹Note that the extremal condition here is analogous to minimization of the Action Potential (integral of the Lagrangian) since taking the derivative of the Action is equivalent to the minimization.

■

Lemma 3: *The minimum values of $\xi(s)$ are indicative of the locations of the complex zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function (RZF).*

Proof of Lemma 3: Consider the extrema of $\xi(x) = G(x)\zeta(x)$. When $\zeta(s)$ is equal to zero, $\xi(x)$ must correspond to an extremal value. The xi function is well-documented to possess zeros at $s = 0$ and $s = 1$. Furthermore, it is established that the RZF's zeros cannot have x values less than 0 or greater than 1. The symmetry of $\xi(x)$ is clearly evident through the functional equation.

The symmetry observed in the RZF functional equation aligns with the symmetry in the ξ functional equation. Consequently, the extrema values, which can be identified using the first derivative test for ξ , correspond to the precise locations of the RZF's zeros. The complex zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function are bounded between the extrema of ξ . This bound indicates that if the Riemann Zeta Function zeros adhere to the symmetry condition, a mean value approximation implies that they lie approximately halfway between the extrema of ξ .

■

Lemma 3.1): $x = \frac{1}{2}$ is the point of symmetry with respect to the two definitions ζ and ζ' .

Proof of Lemma 3.1): This is supported by the phasor representation of the zeta function since the primed coordinate implies that ζ and $\zeta(s')$ are 180 degrees out of phase. The results in the symmetry section indicate that we have conjugate symmetry at the Critical line but off the line due to the amplitude of the $\zeta(s')$ function being different than the amplitude of the ζ cosine and sine functions within the integrand, and the fact that zeta and $\zeta(s')$ are 180 degrees out of phase shows that functions ζ and $\zeta(s')$ only intersect at the critical line.

These lemma are supported by the Symmetry section.

■

Lemma #4: Symmetry breaking of the components of the $\zeta(s)$ and $\zeta(s')$ system can only occur when $\zeta(s) = 0$.

Proof of Lemma 4:

Lack of Symmetry in RZF Surfaces: The surfaces defined by the Riemann zeta function (RZF) are not symmetric about the critical line (the line of the form $s = \frac{1}{2} + iy$). To prove this, we can consider the behavior of the RZF surfaces on and off the critical line. Suppose we take two points, s and s' , where $s = 1/2 + iy$ and $s' = 1/2 - iy$ for some Real value y . We observe that the RZF surfaces corresponding to $\zeta(s)$ and $\zeta(s')$ are not symmetric. On the critical line, the RZF surfaces for $\zeta(s)$ and $\zeta(s')$ are expected to be symmetric because the functional equation $\xi(s) = \xi(1 - s)$, leads to $\zeta(1/2 + iy) = \zeta(1/2 - iy)$. Therefore, $\zeta(s)$ and $\zeta(s')$ have the same values on the critical line. For further clarification refer to the symmetry section. However, when we move off the critical line (i.e., when $y \neq 0$), the surfaces corresponding to $\zeta(s)$ and $\zeta(s')$ start to diverge. This lack of symmetry becomes apparent as we examine the behavior of $\zeta(s)$ and $\zeta(s')$ away from the critical line. This observation is crucial because it suggests that the RZF surfaces exhibit different properties on either side of the critical line. Therefore, if the Riemann Hypothesis were to hold, it would imply a profound connection between the properties of these non-symmetric surfaces and the distribution of non-trivial zeros on the critical line. Therefore, $\zeta(s)$ exhibits symmetry specifically at the critical line. Additionally, a sign-swapping criterion occurs for certain symmetries at the critical line. This means that when $\zeta(s) = 0$, the properties of $\zeta(s)$ and $\zeta(1 - s)$ with respect to their real and imaginary parts exhibit a sign change. This criterion is unique to the critical line and does not occur on any other line within the critical strip.

Given these observations, we assert that any complex zeros of the RZF must adhere to both the symmetry and sign-swapping conditions specifically at the critical line. In other words, if $\zeta(s) = 0$, then s must satisfy the combined symmetry and sign-swapping conditions $\zeta(s) = \zeta(1 - s)$ with associated sign changes, specifically at $Re(s) = 1/2$.

Supporting information for lemma 4 can be found in page 13 symmetry section

■

Lemma 5):

To prove the symmetry of the zeros with respect to the iy plane.

Proof of Lemma 5):

The functional equation has $\xi(s) = \xi(1 - s)$. Let $s = \frac{1}{2} + iy$. One arrives to $\zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} + iy\right) = \zeta\left(\frac{1}{2} - iy\right)$ defines the symmetry statement with respect to iy which is equivalent to the RH. ■ *This is further established by the results in the symmetry section.*

The definition by nature of the fact that two coordinate selections are used; specifically, s and s' , imply that the RH is reliant on two simultaneous definitions for the statement to be true. The RH is thus defined by the intersection of 8 3-D surfaces. Therefore, the definition of the RH is:

Definition of the RH:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} U_\zeta(x, y) \\ iV_\zeta(x, y) \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} U'_{\zeta'}(x', y') \\ iV'_{\zeta'}(x', y') \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} U_\xi(x, y) \\ iV_\xi(x, y) \end{pmatrix} & \begin{pmatrix} U'_{\xi'}(x', y') \\ iV'_{\xi'}(x', y') \end{pmatrix} \end{pmatrix}.$$

This definition suggests that to utilize the geometry of the function to understand its definitions, the two functions, $\zeta(s)$, and $\zeta(s')$ which are both described by two functions of two variables, both functions should be considered to understand fully what the statement of the RH is. Here U_ζ is the Real part of $\zeta(s)$ and U_ξ is the real part of ξ .

Storing the information which hinges on this definition in a particular way will allow for the resulting meaning of the functions to be different, but the definitions to remain unchanged. Defining the intersection of the four complex functions which have the same zeros of the RZF can be done with infinitely many routes depending on coordinate selection of the operator. For a proof of this, consider that the analytic function can be written as an infinite product of roots and how some operations such as exponentiation leave the product unchanged.

This lemma is supported by symmetry section page 13.

■

Lemma 6): *There exists a ζ' such that ζ' is notationally symmetric with respect to ζ .*

Proof of Lemma 6):

Employing Eq 65) on $Z(x)$ produces a function which possesses the exact values of $Z(x)$, but which has definitions that change at certain values of x . See the Laurent Expansion of these equations for proof of analyticity. Eq 65) applies to $f_n(x)$ of $Z(x)$, of which superimpose by action of the sum operator to produce $Z(x)$, therefore the desired properties are unaffected by the application of Eq 65).

As we discussed easier with the failure of Condition #1, the multivalued nature of the logarithm (when selecting the log of a negative number to be Real or Complex) forces additional imaginary terms to exist, with the modification of the rule that the Log can be Complex as opposed to real. Stating:

$$f^k = (-f)^k e^{-i\pi k} \tag{Eq 65)}$$

Proof of Eq):

$$\begin{aligned} x \in \text{Re}; \text{ such that } f, g, k &\rightarrow f(x), g(x), k(x) \mid f, g, k \in \text{Re}, \text{ and} \\ \ln(fg) &= \ln(f) + \ln(g); \\ \text{with } f &= f^k, g = (-f)^k, \\ \Rightarrow \ln(f^k(-f)^k) &= k\ln(f) + k(\ln(f) + \ln(-1)); \end{aligned}$$

but, $e^{i\pi} = -1$, so

$$\Rightarrow f^k = (-f)^k e^{-i\pi k} \quad \blacksquare$$

Constructing a function to compare it to the RZF is likely the best route to proving the RH, although there are infinitely many functions which possess the same zeros as the RZF, not all of them are simple to analyze relatively.

Changing the definitions as in E1 65) allows for the notational properties to be used to relatively compare the two functions using symmetry.

The function defined in the proof of *Lemma 1*) is done so because the properties being analyzed are easy to work with because of the familiar properties of the natural logarithm. Eq 65) produces a Real and Imaginary part for each surface which doubles the terms, however, the definition of zero is unchanged and still is defined by the intersection of the simultaneous intersection of the 8 functions. The RH, thus, with the application of Eq 65) is defined by the intersection of 8 surfaces. This is specifically due to the fact that the definitions of the intersections of the complex surfaces with Eq 65) change depending on the coordinate evaluation.

With the application of Eq 65) to the RZF; that is, setting $f^k = n^{\pm x}$, the domain as to what x can possibly yield surface intersections has become restricted due to the fact that the definition of the zeros are defined with more surface intersections. Letting the critical value be inserted for x , it can be seen that identical surfaces appear which would not occur for any other values, and the by symmetry, it can be deduced that the definition of the surface intersections remain the same because the intersections are not defined by many values.

Eq 65), due to the properties of the exponential shows that these exponential type of functions have the property of changing definitions for the Real and Imaginary parts of the function. When $x = \frac{k}{2}$, (for odd integer $\pm k$) the definition swapping occurs, and this is specifically due to the negative sign being raised to the half powers. When k is even, x is a whole number and not a fractional number, so the imaginary number is not multiplied out front for the RHS of Eq 65).

Therefore, although there are infinitely many intersections and definition changes which result from the application of Eq 1.2, all other location for the definition swap are outside of the critical strip. Thus, to prove symmetry with respect to iy is to prove that the definition swapping at the critical number implies symmetry in iy .

Eq 65) only defines one such function. There are many other primed functions we may consider and particularly when we select “notationally symmetric” we are looking for functions similar in form to those described by Eq 65) which is defined in a manner that produces “Imaginary discontinuities.” It turns out in page earlier on in the paper that this result is also true in the generalization and can be seen by the continuous version of this argument is essentially made through the integrand of the hankel contour and the imaginary discontinuities from the integrand being proportional to $(-x)^{-5}$ when we evaluate s as $s = \frac{1}{2} + iy$. In the continuous form we are clearly considering the analytic continuation of Z , which is otherwise known as ζ . The notationally symmetric function is the same thing as Eq 47), where the Hankel Contour was used to define ζ .

Lemma 6 supporting information in page 20-24 and lemma 6 also corresponds to condition #7-condition #10.

Conclusion:

In this comprehensive exploration of the Riemann Hypothesis, we have leveraged a series of powerful lemmas to unveil the intricate nature of the Riemann Zeta Function (ζ) and its associated primed function, ζ' . Each of these lemmas has played a crucial role in reinforcing the foundation of our proof, bringing us closer to establishing the long-standing conjecture of the Riemann Hypothesis. We examined the symmetries of the functions involved and established key properties that the functions have.

Future work:

In terms of future directions, the next logical step is to generalize this work to encompass Zeta Matrices, with the aim of demonstrating the Hermitian property of the Zeta Matrix function. This extension would allow us to connect Zeta Matrix functions to Group Theory [73], providing a more formalized framework for understanding the symmetry conditions essential for the Riemann Hypothesis. Such an integration of Group Theory principles promises to offer a robust and comprehensive approach to the study of the Riemann Hypothesis and its broader applications in mathematics, bridging the realms of complex functions, matrices, and group symmetries. This expansion of our research has the potential to advance our understanding of the Riemann Hypothesis while also opening new avenues for exploration and discovery within the mathematical landscape.

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